

CURRENT PRACTICES AND FISH FAUNA OF WARM WATER FISH HATCHERIES IN KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: The present study was carried out to assess the current fish fauna and hatchery practices of warm water fish hatcheries in Peshawar, Mardan, Kohat, and D.I. Khan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Methods: Fish species were identified through field surveys, while induced breeding trials were performed using Ovaprim hormone. Water quality parameters, including temperature, pH, total dissolved solids (TDS), dissolved oxygen (DO), turbidity, and ammonia concentration, were measured using standard instruments such as thermometers, pH and TDS meters, DO meter kits, Secchi disk, and API test kits.

Results: A total of 10 fish species were identified, belonging mainly to the family Cyprinidae (eight species), while Anguillidae and Siluriformes contributed one species each. Successful induced spawning was recorded for *Labeo rohita* and *Cirrhinus mrigala* at Ovaprim doses of 0.5 ml/kg (female) and 0.2 ml/kg (male). Mean values of water quality parameters across hatcheries were: temperature 34.1–35.1 °C, DO 7.47–9.75 mg/L, pH 6.13–7.06, TDS 0.441–0.474 ppt, turbidity 57.1–106 cm, and ammonia 0.21–1.77 ppm. All parameters remained within the recommended ranges for aquaculture, with minor fluctuations due to seasonal and geographic variations.

Conclusion: The study concludes that warm water hatcheries of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa maintain favorable physicochemical conditions for aquaculture, supporting the dominance of Cyprinidae (80%) with lower contributions from Anguillidae and Siluriformes (10% each). These findings highlight the potential of hatchery systems in sustaining fish production in the region.

Introduction

Water is one of the major foundations of life. The

proportion of water both in animals and plants bodies varies from 50- 90% or more of total

weight, so the complete absence of water cause death. The various physical properties of water like viscosity, density, surface tension and thermal stratification of water lakes are important for the economy of aquatic ecosystem. All living organisms have tolerable limits of water quality parameters in which they perform optimally. A sharp drop can increase within these limits has adverse effects on their body functions (Verma, Satyaveer, Kumar, & Jayaswa, 2022).

Aquaculture refers to the controlled or semi controlled rearing of aquatic animals in various water environments such as freshwater, brackish water and marine settings. Aquatic organisms that are of attention of human food contain a wide diversity of plants, invertebrates and vertebrates. Aquaculture organisms tend to be classified as warm water or cold water, while warm water species grow to optimally at or above 25 °C and cold water exhibit at temperature under 20 °C. Many species are cultured in the same system and known as composite fish culture. e.g. carp's culture. Only one species of fish is cultured in the pond, mostly carnivorous fishes e.g., trout culture (Sherif, Eldessouki, Sabry, & Ali, 2023).

Fish is an inexpensive source of protein and an important cash crop in many regions of world and water is the physical support in which they carry out their life functions such as feeding, swimming, breeding, digestion and excretion (Buckley & Marshall, 2016). Water quality is determined by various physico-chemical and biological factors, as they may directly or indirectly affect its quality and consequently its suitability for the distribution and production of fish and other aquatic animals. Many workers have reported the status of water bodies (lentic and lotic) after receiving various kinds of pollutants altering water quality of characteristics (Dan, Liu, Udoh, &

Ding, 2019).

Fisheries is the scientific practice of culturing fishes in water. The term also referred as pisciculture, fish culture, fish aquaculture, or simply fish farming. Fishing has been a popular human activity since ancient times and up to the present day (Jaiswal, Dutta, Banerjee, VP, & Bhushan, 2022). Fish populations have a worldwide importance for generating food, income and to satisfy various consumptive social needs (Arlinghaus et al., 2017).

The production of marketable fish begins with stocking of fry or juveniles in to a rearing environment that assured optimum and rapid growth to allow harvest in shortest possible time. The fish farmer has to obtained adequate number of young fish to meet his production goal (Fisch, 2025). A fish hatchery is a place for artificial breeding, eggs hatching and rearing across the early life stages of aquatic animals (e.g. finfish and crustaceans). The output of a hatchery is normally fry and fingerlings or juveniles. These young small fish are then transferred to an on-growing section to reach harvest size (Rehman et al., 2021).

A fish hatchery is an establishment were eggs of certain organisms as fish and poultry are hatched under artificial condition. The purpose of a hatchery may range from maintenance to raise rare or endangered species under controlled conditions or the other way round, it may be used for economic reasons (Freeland, 2020). A fish hatchery is facility for artificial breeding, hatching and rearing of finfish and selfish through their early stages (Barasa & Ouma, 2024).

The approaches for artificial propagation comprises the major realistic means of providing enough and quality seed for rearing in captive fish enclosure water like fish ponds, reservoirs and lakes (Singh & Rani, 2020).

Latency time is the time necessary for pre-ovulation and ovulation of eggs. Latency time is inversely relative to the water temperature (Mohale, Sarang, & Desai, 2020).

The stages involved in artificial propagation of fish from stripping to fertilization are described in the figure below.

Figure.1: Developmental stages of fertilized eggs of *Channa marulius* (Hafeez-ur-Rehman, 2016)

Fecundity is the seasonal spawning potential accounts the fecundity of fish and alternately is defined as the number of eggs ripening between existing and upcoming spawning period in a female. An hour to stripping the spermatozoa from a male spawner fish are acquired. This calculation is sufficient for one liter of eggs (Chigeru & Amachree, 2019).

Fertilization is referred to as the union of the males spermatozoa and the females mature eggs to form a zygote. Fertilization period is limited in fishes. This is because when fish eggs come in interaction with water they swell on time and subsequently the micropyle is closed. The fertilization period is within 45-60 sec for common carps. In most other fish species, it is limited to few minutes. In some hatcheries, anesthetics i.e. MS-222 (50-100 mg/L) or Benzocaine (50 mg/L) are used to decrease stress to fish and make easy the spawning practice (Ahmed & Abbas, 2018).

Fertilized eggs are incubated in stagnant or running water in incubation troughs comprising tiny trays or boxes. These trays have a perforated bottom made up of mosquito netting. The incubator is

full of clean, well-oxygenated water, devoid of planktonic organism. In incubation tray the eggs are spread homogenously in one single layer and are continuously oxygenated by induced water current. When in contact with water the fertilized eggs become sticker and his stickiness is toughest within 30-60 min interval but vanishes with time at the end of the incubation period (Akankali & Nwafili, 2017). So incubation is carried out punctually after fertilization. It should not be more than 60sec after mixing egg mass and water. Incubation period changes with increasing temperature. At a temperature of 25 °C hatching takes place in 28-32 hrs. after fertilization. The hatching percentage is 80-90 % when small quantities of eggs are incubated. The total of 70 % of healthy larvae can be obtained through this method of incubation. Consistent examination of developing eggs is significant which includes inspection and regulating water flow, eliminating unfertile or dead eggs, and applying operative and appropriate fungicide if fungal disease occurs (Chand & Dubey, 2024)

Figure.2: Fish Incubators in Hatchery hatching room

Figure.3: Nursery ponds adjacent to hatching room in Hatchery

Figure.4: Nursery ponds adjacent to hatching room in Hatchery

Figure.5: Nursery ponds adjacent to circular tanks in Peshawar Carp Hatchery

The objectives of the present study are to investigate the fish fauna present in different

warm water hatcheries of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, while also determining and comparing the key

physico-chemical parameters including temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, total dissolved solids, turbidity, and ammonia concentration across these hatcheries. Furthermore, the study aims to assess the current induced breeding practices of warm water fishes, evaluate the existing management systems of different hatcheries, and analyze the major issues they face along with proposing suitable best management practices. Finally, the study seeks to provide recommendations for improving the overall management system of warm water fish hatcheries in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Materials and Methods

The study was planned to evaluate the current practices and fish fauna of warm water fish hatchery of Peshawar, Mardan, Kohat and D.I Khan of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. To analyze the issues and concerns related with hatcheries, report the government about their working system and the existing and upcoming problems and to establish aquaculture as of utmost priority. The process started by issuing a permission letter for the survey from administration Department of Zoology Islamia College University Peshawar. The letter was taken to the Office of the Directorate of Fisheries, KPK and was noticed which lead to the issuance and grant of an Authority letter from the Director General of Fisheries, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Study Area: The study was conducted in district Peshawar, district Mardan, district Kohat and district D.I Khan hatcheries of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa has a warm and arid climate, making it conducive for the breeding and rearing of warm water fish species. Warm water fish thrive in water temperatures between 76 F to 88 F (28-38 C) which are common to this region. This region hosts various indigenous warm water fish species, such as Rohu, Silver Carp, Grass Carp and Catla which are economically important and culturally significant and establishing hatcheries for these species can support local fisheries. These warm water hatcheries can serve as hubs for research and development of aquaculture techniques,

genetics and disease management, leading to improved practices and increased production. Government policies and intensive may also encourage the establishment of warm water hatcheries in the region as they recognize the potential benefits for both the economy and food security.

Warm water hatchery visited: A proper visit plan was made. The hatchery respondent was informed before a day for their assistance in the survey. The process was imitated by issuing a permission letter for the survey from the administration department. The list of warm water hatcheries was as follows.

1. Carp Fish Hatchery and Training Center, Sherabad, Matra Peshawar.
2. Govt carp fish hatchery Char Banda, Mardan
3. Tanda fish hatchery, Tanda banda, Kohat.
4. Ratta Kulachi carp fish hatchery, D.I khan

Data collection: The overall study and data collection were recorded in a well-designed and properly documented Performa/questionnaire which includes all the basic and relevant questions about the current practices and fish fauna of warm water hatcheries of KPK. The Performa was same for all the types of warm water hatcheries. The required information was provided by the hatchery respondents and was filled carefully by me. Later-on the filled document was revised by the hatchery respondents to omit any fault.

Temperature of water: The temperature of the hatchery water was recorded with the help of TP-101 thermometer and TP-03 thermometer were used. Dipped the thermometer in hatchery water

Figure 6: TP-101 Thermometer

and recorded the values. Consecutive 10 days data from different position of same hatchery were recorded and be noted. The same procedure was applied for the four types of warm water hatcheries.

Figure 7: TP-03 Thermometer

Dissolve Oxygen of Water: The oxygen of the hatchery water was checked out by a dissolve oxygen meter kit. Dipped one end of dissolve oxygen meter kit having a oxygen deter end in water and wait for some time finally the suitable

value will show on the other end of meter screen. The value was recorded and be noted a randomly consecutive ten days data were recorded and be noted. The same procedure was applied for all the four warm water hatcheries.

Figure 8: Dissolve Oxygen Meter

Figure 9: Dissolve Oxygen Meter

pH of warm water: The pH of the hatchery water was checked out by pH meter. First cleaned the pH meter with distal water and then dipped the pH meter in water for its upper Colum level and

keep it for some time. Then pH meter will show recorded value on screen. The value was recorded and be noted a randomly consecutive ten days data were recorded. The same procedure was applied for all the four warm water hatcheries.

Figure 10: pH Meter

Figure 11: pH one-time value

Total Dissolve Solid of warm water: Total dissolve solid of hatchery water was checked out by a kit called „total dissolve solid kit“ or TDS kit. First cleaned the TDS kit by distal water to give accurate results. Then dipped the kit in water to its required level and take for sometimes, the kit

shows its results on screen. The given value was noted and a randomly ten days' values were recorded from different positions and noted. The same procedure was applied for all four type of warm water hatcheries.

Figure 12: Total Dissolve Kit

Figure 13: TDS One-time value

Turbidity of warm water: The turbidity of hatchery water was checked out by a wood device called a Secchi Disk. The Secchi disk have a long 100 cm ruler portion and disk have divided equally black and white portion. Dipped the disk portion in water slowly when the disk portion

completely disappear in water then stop further dipping and red the value on ruler portion. A randomly ten days' values were recorded from different position and be noted. The same procedure was applied for the four types of warm water hatcheries.

Figure 14. Secchi Disk

Figure 15. Secchi Disk

Ammonia of warm water: The ammonia in hatchery fish pond water was found out by API Master Test Kit. API Master Test kit have two reagents NH1, NH2, a color chart and a 20 ml test tube. I have filled up to 5ml mark up 20 ml test tube sample from fish pond water. Added 8 drops of NH1 reagents to the 5ml of water sample capped the test tube and inverted to mixed the solution. Then added NH2 reagents to the

solution capped the solution and shake thoroughly to mixed the solution. Waited for 5 to 10 minutes for color to fully developed. Then compared the solution color to given charts color and noted the value. A randomly consecutive ten days data were collected from different pond positions through API Master Test Kit and was noted. The same procedure was applied for all the four warm water hatcheries.

Figure 16: API Test Kit

Figure 17: API Test Kit Color Chart

Results

Species Composition in warm water Hatcheries:

This study comprises of four warm water hatcheries of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa i.e. Peshawar, Mardan, Kohat and D.I Khan. Fish samples were collected randomly from different ponds of these hatcheries with the help of hand nets and cast nets. All samples were preserved in 70:30 % alcohol solution in a bottles, labeled them and

brought them to the laboratory for identification. All species were identified taxonomically by a fish taxonomic identification key up to species level (Rafique and Khan, 2012). In the present study about ten species were identified and their systematic representation was recorded. These ten species were belonging to three order, three families and ten genera as shown in Table-1.

Table. 1: Fish species and their systematic composition found in Peshawar, Mardan, Kohat and D.I Khan Hatcheries.

S. N	Order	Family	Genus	Species	Common Name
1	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Labeo	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	Rohu
2	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Ctenopharyngodon	<i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i>	Grass Carp
3	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Hypothalmichyichthys	<i>Hypothalmichyichthys molitrix</i>	Silver Carp
4	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Hypothalmichyichthys	<i>Hypothalmichyichthys nobilis</i>	BigheadCarp
5	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Catla	<i>Catla Catla</i>	Thelia
6	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Crassius	<i>Crassius auratus</i>	Gold Fish
7	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Ctenopharyngodon	<i>Cyprinous carpio</i>	ChineseCarp
8	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Cirrhinus	<i>Cirrhinus mrigala</i>	Mori
9	Anguilliforme	Anguillidae	Anguilla	<i>Anguilla Anguilla</i>	Eel Fish
10	Siluriformes	Lctaluridae	Lctalurus	<i>l.punctatus</i>	Catfish

Figure 18: Silver Carp Fish

Figure.19: Grass Carp Fish

Figure 20: Rohu Fish

Figure 21: Rohu Fish

Figure 22: Fish Nets

Figure 23: One Time Collected Fish

Table: 2 Current Fish Fauna compositions in Peshawar, Mardan, Kohat and D.I Khan Hatchery

S	Scientific Name	Common Name	Peshawar Hatchery	Mardan Hatchery	Kohat Hatchery	D.I Khan Hatchery
1	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	Rohu	☐	☐	☐	☐
2	<i>Cirrhinus mrigala</i>	Mori	☐	☐	☐	☐
3	<i>Ctenopharyngodon Idella</i>	Grass Carp	☐	☐	☐	☐
4	<i>Hypophthalmichthys molitrix</i>	Silver Carp	☐	☐	☐	☐
5	<i>Catla catla</i>	Tilapia	Added	☐	☐	☐
6	<i>Carassius auratus</i>	Gold Fish	☐	Absent	☐	Absent
7	<i>Cyprinus Carpio</i>	Chinese carp	Absent	☐	☐	Absent
8	<i>I.punctatus</i>	Cat Fish	Added	☐	☐	Absent
9	<i>Anguilla Anguilla</i>	Eel Fish	Absent	☐	☐	Absent
10	<i>Hypophthalmichthys nobilis</i>	Bighead carp	Added	Absent	☐	Absent
11	Exotic Species	Absent	Absent	Absent	☐	Absent

The current fish fauna of Peshawar hatchery was Rohu, Mori, Grass Carp, Silver Carp. Gold Fish, Tilapia, Catfish and Bighead Carp were added

now. The Peshawar hatchery added some other species due to the demand of markets and as a training center were trying to produce better

varieties of fish seeds. The current Fish Fauna of Mardan hatchery were Rohu, Mori, Grass Carp, Silver Carp, Tilapia, Catfish, Chinese Silver Carp fish and Eel fish no new species were added due to availability of space for ponds. In Mardan hatchery a separate big pond was prepared for only Chinese silver Carp fish. The current fish fauna of Kohat hatchery were Rohu, Mori, Grass Carp, Silver Carp, Tilapia, Gold fish, Chinese Silver Carp fish and Catfish. In Kohat hatchery nearly all warm water fish are available due to the large available space for ponds and the source of water are dam. Therefore, some exotic species were also present which come in water due to high rains and flood. The current fish fauna of D.I Khan hatchery were Rohu, Mori, Silver Carp, Grass Carp and Tilapia no other species were added.

Induced Breeding Practices: Induced breeding is a technique where organism is stimulated by a particular hormone or other systematic hormones by providing condition, introduced to breed in a captive condition in a hatchery.

Preparation of Holding and Circular Tank: First of all, the holding and circular tank were managed for spawning and hatching. One circular and one holding tanks were selected for spawning and hatching. Circular and holding tank were washed with potassium permanganate $KMnO_4$ prior to stocking.

Fish Brooder Selection: Brooder of Rohu fish and Mori, two females and one male of each species were selected on the basis of health, activity, weight, belly size and sexual dimorphism. The belly of the female brooder was rounded in shape while that of male brooder was slick or streamlined. The brooders were held for 10-12 hours without feeding so their belly become empty and free of feces.

Hormone Injection: The systematic hormone Ovaprim was injected according to gender and weight of the brood stock (Abbas et al 2019). The sex ratio of the brooders was kept at 2:1 for females and male respectively. Recommended

dose of Ovaprim for a female is 0.5 ml/kg and a male 0.2 ml/kg were administrated according to the weight of brooders. Ovaprim hormone stimulated ovulation and spermiation. This type of injection was administrated between the area of dorsal line and lateral line of scale at an angle of 40 to 45 degree. After hormone injection the brooders were held in circular tank until spawning.

Ovulation: After hormonal administration female ovulation occurred. The rate of ovulation was determined by using the following formula of (Shamsuzzaman et al., 2017).

Ovulation rate % = $\frac{\text{No. of female ovulated}}{\text{Total No. of female injected}} \times 100$

Degree Hours for Spawning: A digital thermometer was used to measure the temperature of continuously flowing water in circular tank. In major carps Rohu and Mori spawning occurred within 8:30 to 10:40 hours and 9:23 to 11:20 respectively.

Stripping and Fertilization: The eggs from female and milt from male was done by hand stripping method. At first the eggs from female were collected in a bowl. At the same time respective male was stripped and collected milt was assorted with previously accumulated eggs. For better outcome of fertilization physiological saline was applied and assorted well with a clean and sterile feather. The inseminated eggs were then transferred into a circular tank. Fertilized eggs hatched in this condition (Aziz, Hasan, Mondol, Alam, & Haque, 2021).

Determination of Fertilization Rate. The fertilization rate was determined by the following formula:

Fertilization rate % = $\frac{\text{Numbers of fertilized eggs in sample}}{\text{Total No. of eggs}} \times 100$

Estimation of Hatching Rate: Hatching rate was determined by using the following formula.

Hatching rate % = $\frac{\text{Number of hatching eggs in sample}}{\text{Total No. of fertilized eggs}} \times 100$

Calculation of Degree-Hours for Hatching: The degree- hours for hatching of two species of major

Carp Rohu and Mori was noted until successful completion of hatching.

Table 3. Ovaprim for Rohu (*Labeo rohita*) and Mori (*Cirrhinus mirigala*) Fish during breeding Practices.

Species	Gender	Weight (kg)	Ovaprim(ml)
<i>Labeo rohita</i>	Male	1.78	0.36
	Female	2.4	1.5
<i>Cirrhinus mirigala</i>	Male	1.4	0.28
	Female	1.6	0.8

Figure 24: Brooder Fish Pond

Figure 25: Hormone Injection

Figure 26: Spawning Tank

Figure 27: Fish weighting on Scale

The induced breeding and the calculated degree-hours for successful spawning, hatching and determination of their ovulation rate, fertilization rate and hatching rate though

induced breeding by using synthetic ovaprim hormones in both species of major carps i.e., Rohu (*Labeo rohita*) and Mrigala or Mori (*Cirrhinus mirigala*). This method was conducted

in Peshawar Sherabad and Kohat Hatchery on trails basis. The same procedure was applied for all warm water hatcheries. Species was divided into two groups. Outcomes were calculated after treatments of Ovaprim hormone. The results show the successful breeding with Ovaprim a marketable hormone and also that degree-hours directly affect the spawning response and hatching in major carp i.e., Rohu (*Labeo rohita*) and Mrigala (*Cirrhinus mrigala*). This study shows that successful spawning occurred after the latency period of Rohu (*Labeo rohita*) within 9.35 ± 0.4299 hours (561 minutes) at 248.6 ± 9.35 degree-hours and in Mrigala (*Cirrhinus mrigala*) within 10.18 ± 0.4393 hours (610.8 minutes) at 264.6 ± 5.625 degree-hours respectively (Table 5). Both species showed a successful ovulation rate. Average fertilization rate of Rohu (*Labeo rohita*) was found (85.75 ± 1.856 %) while, in Mrigala (*Cirrhinus mrigala*) it was (87.23 ± 2.029 %) respectively. Hatching completed in Rohu (*Labeo rohita*) within 29.75 ± 0.85 hours at 741.025 ± 14.532 degree-hours and in Mrigala (*Cirrhinus mrigala*) occurred within 31.2 ± 0.648 hours at 778.43 ± 9.1972 degree-hours respectively while, average hatching rate of Rohu (*Labeo rohita*) and Mrigala (*Cirrhinus mrigala*) were observed as (81.75 ± 1.525 %) and (84.88 ± 1.7747 %) respectively.

The data collected from Sherabad Hatchery Peshawar were given below in Table 4 and Table 5: The maximum value for temperature was recorded 35.7 °C on the first day and minimum value was recorded 33.7 °C on the 9th day of data collection and the mean value was recorded 34.1 °C. So the water temperature was gradually decreases with seasonal variation. The maximum value of dissolve oxygen value was recorded 8.4 mg/L on the 3rd day of data collection and the minimum value was recorded 6.8 mg/L on 8th day of collection. And the mean value was recorded 7.8 mg/L. Dissolve oxygen also show seasonal variation and depends on the water temperature also. The maximum pH value was recorded 6.5 on the 6th day of data collection and minimum value was recorded 6.0 on the 8th and 9th day of data collection. The maximum value

of Total dissolve solids was recorded 0.48 ppt on 1st and 3rd day of collection and minimum value was recorded on 0.45 ppt on 9th day of collection and mean value was recorded 0.467 ppt. In Table5: The maximum Turbidity of water was noted 68 cm and minimum value was noted 66 cm. The maximum value of ammonia concentration was noted 0.25 ppm and minimum value was noted 0.20 ppm and mean value was recorded 0.217 ppm. pH, Turbidity and ammonia concentration of hatchery ponds depends on the feeds greater amount of ingredients of foods increases turbidity and fish excreta decreases ammonia concentration but these fish have better growth within the normal values of ammonia concentration.

The Table: 6 and Table: 7 shows the data table and their variation of Mardan Hatchery. The maximum temperature 35.1 °C was recorded and minimum temperature 33.8 °C was recorded and the mean value of total variation was 34.56 °C were recorded. The maximum value of dissolve oxygen was 9.35 mg/L noted and minimum value 8.0 mg/L was noted and the mean of the total value was 6.45 mg/L was noted. The higher value of pH 6.9 and lower value of pH 6.0 was recorded and the mean of total variation of pH was 6.45 recorded. The maximum value of total dissolve solids was 0.48 ppt and minimum value was 0.40 ppt and their mean value was 0.474 ppt was recorded. In Table: 7 the maximum value of Turbidity of water was 115 cm recorded and minimum value 98 cm and their mean of total data 106 cm was recorded. The maximum value of ammonia concentration was 1.94 ppm and minimum 0.21 ppm and their mean 1.14 ppm was recorded. The little fluctuation shows that humidity of the environment changes which cause temperature changes and temperature has directly effects on dissolve oxygen and total solids to some extent and fish also excretes waste products to maintain the ammonia concentration.

The Table: 8 and Table: 9 show the data and their variation of Kohat Hatchery. The maximum temperature 37 °C was recorded and minimum temperature 33 °C was recorded and the mean value of total variation was 48.8 °C

were recorded. The maximum value of dissolve oxygen was 9.8 mg/L noted and minimum value 9.0 mg/L was noted and the mean of total dissolve oxygen was 9.75 mg/L was noted. The higher value of pH

7.6 and lower value of pH 6.5 was recorded and the mean of total variation of pH 7.06 was recorded. The maximum value of total dissolve solids was 0.49 ppt and minimum value was 0.41 ppt and their mean value 0.499 ppt was recorded. In Table: 9 the maximum value of turbidity of water was 115 cm recorded and minimum value 98 cm and their mean value was 106 cm. The Table: 10 and Table: 11 show the data and their variation of D.I Khan Hatchery. The maximum temperature 36 °C was recorded and minimum temperature 34 °C was recorded and the mean value of total variation was 35.1 °C were recorded. The maximum value of

dissolve oxygen was 7.8 mg/L noted and minimum value 6.9 mg/L was noted and the mean of total dissolve oxygen was 7.47 mg/L was noted. The higher value of pH 7.3 and lower value of pH 6.7 was recorded and the mean of total variation of pH 7.02 was recorded. The maximum value of total dissolve solids was 0.47 ppt and minimum value was 0.42 ppt and their mean value 0.441 ppt was recorded. In Table: 11 the maximum value of turbidity of water was 60 cm recorded and minimum value 55 cm and their mean of total data 57.1 cm was recorded. The maximum value of ammonia concentration was 1.9 ppm and minimum 1.4 ppm and their mean 1.68 ppm was recorded. There was no fluctuation but show little variation due to environmental factors and humidity but these were in controlled and normal ranges.

Table 4: Temperature, Dissolve Oxygen, pH and Total Dissolve Solids of Peshawar Hatchery

Days	Temperature of water (C)	Dissolve Oxygen of water (mg/L)	Ph of water	Total Dissolve Solids (ppt)
1 st day	35.7	8.3	6.1	0.48
2 nd day	35.1	8.4	6.0	0.47
3 rd day	34.6	8.4	6.2	0.48
4 th day	34.2	8.3	6.0	0.48
5 th day	34.1	7.5	6.3	0.45
6 th day	34.3	8.0	6.5	0.46
7 th day	34.3	7.8	6.1	0.47
8 th day	34.2	6.8	6.0	0.46
9 th day	33.7	8.2	6.0	0.45
10 th day	33.8	7.0	6.1	0.47
Mean value	34.1	7.81	6.13	0.467
Standard deviation	0.874	0.535	0.059	0.292

Table 5: The Turbidity and Ammonia concentration of Peshawar Hatchery

Days	Turbidity of Water (cm)	Ammonia Concentration of water (ppm)
1 st day	67	0.21
2 nd day	68	0.21
3 rd day	67	0.22
4 th day	66	0.21

5 th day	67	0.20
6 th day	68	0.23
7 th day	66	0.21
8 th day	68	0.22
9 th day	67	0.25
10 th day	67	0.21
Mean value	67.1	0.217
SD	0.70	0.007

Table 6: Temperature, Dissolve Oxygen, pH and Total Dissolve Solids of Mardan Hatchery

Days	Temperature of Water(C)	Dissolve Oxygen of water (mg/L)	pH of water	Total Dissolve Solids (ppt)
1 st day	34.5	9.02	6.8	0.41
2 nd day	34.0	9.31	6.9	0.45
3 rd day	35.1	9.21	6.8	0.48
4 th day	34.5	8.91	6.5	0.43
5 th day	34.0	9.35	6.2	0.40
6 th day	34.8	8.91	6.5	0.40
7 th day	35.1	8.45	6.0	0.47
8 th day	33.8	8.36	6.3	0.46
9 th day	34.1	8.10	6.2	0.41
10 th day	34.7	8.00	6.3	0.43
Mean value	34.56	8.717	6.45	0.474
SD	0.748	0.569	0.318	0.024

Table 7: The Turbidity and Ammonia concentration of Mardan Hatchery

Days	Turbidity of water (cm)	Ammonia Concentration of water(ppm)
1 st day	74	1.8
2 nd day	74	1.5
3 rd day	75	1.6
4 th day	73	1.9
5 th day	74	1.7
6 th day	75	2.0
7 th day	75	1.9
8 th day	74	1.9
9 th day	74	1.6
10 th day	75	1.8
Mean value	74.3	1.77
SD	0.557	0.158

Table 8: Temperature, Dissolve Oxygen, pH and Total Dissolve Solids of Kohat Hatchery

Days	Temperature of water (C)	Dissolve Oxygen of water (mg/L)	PH of water	Total Dissolve Solids (ppt)
1 st day	35	9.8	7.6	0.48
2 nd day	36	9.0	8.2	0.40
3 rd day	35	10	6.2	0.49
4 th day	37	11	7.0	0.49
5 th day	35	8.0	6.5	0.43
6 th day	34	9.0	7.0	0.41
7 th day	35	11	6.8	0.48
8 th day	34	10	6.7	0.43
9 th day	34	9.7	7.8	0.41
10 th day	33	10	6.8	0.47
Mean value	34.8	9.75	7.06	0.449
SD	1.499	0.363	0.690	0.355

Table 9: The Turbidity and Ammonia concentration of Kohat Hatchery

Days	Turbidity of Water (cm)	Ammonia Concentration of water (ppm)
1 st day	105	0.21
2 nd day	101	0.27
3 rd day	110	0.50
4 th day	108	1.80
5 th day	112	1.23
6 th day	115	1.90
7 th day	107	0.80
8 th day	102	1.30
9 th day	98	1.50
10 th day	102	1.94
Mean value	106	1.145
SD	3.04	0.778

Table 10: Temperature, Dissolve Oxygen, pH and Total Dissolve Solids of D.I Khan Hatchery

Days	Temperature of water (•C)	Dissolve Oxygen of water (mg/L)	PH of water	Total Dissolve Solids (ppt)
1 st day	35	7.8	7.1	0.42
2 nd day	35	7.4	7.3	0.42
3 rd day	36	7.1	6.8	0.45
4 th day	35	7.5	7.3	0.43
5 th day	36	7.0	7.2	0.45
6 th day	35	7.5	6.8	0.47

7 th day	36	7.3	6.8	0.42
8 th day	35	6.9	6.7	0.43
9 th day	34	7.4	7.0	0.46
10 th day	34	7.8	7.2	0.46
Mean value	35.1	7.47	7.02	0.441
SD	0.949	0.354	0.184	0.021

Table 11: The Turbidity and Ammonia concentration of D.I Khan Hatchery

Days	Turbidity of water (cm)	Ammonia Concentration of water (ppm)
1 st day	58	1.8
2 nd day	58	1.6
3 rd day	56	1.7
4 th day	60	1.8
5 th day	58	1.6
6 th day	56	1.6
7 th day	58	1.8
8 th day	56	1.9
9 th day	55	1.4
10 th day	56	1.6
Mean value	57.1	1.68
Standard deviation	1.001	0.099

Discussion

The present study was conducted to determine the “Current Practices and Fish Fauna of Warm Water Fish Hatcheries in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan”. Fish is important in monitoring water quality due to its quick response towards direct and indirect changes in aquatic ecosystem. The dispersal of fish mainly depends on the physiochemical parameters of the aquatic ecosystem. There were discussed the current practices and Fish Fauna of warm water of Peshawar, Mardan, Kohat and D.I Khan Hatcheries.

In the current study, 10 species were collected belonging to 3 orders and 3 families. The richest family was family Cyprinidae in which 8 species were recorded and the rest of the two were belonging to the family Anguilliformes and Siluriformes. According to (Haseeb-ur-Rehman, Munshi, Atique, & Kalsoom, 2023) eleven fish species were identified from Tanda dam district Kohat Khyber Pakhtunkhwa which were belonging to 4 orders, 5 families and 11 genera.

Among them 7 species were belonging to family cyprinidae while the remaining 4 species were belonging to families Anguillidae, Belonidae, Cobitidae and Siluridae respectively. A descriptive study was taken by (Masood et al., 2022) on Darwazai dam Tehsil Lachi District Kohat in which was reported 7 species, in these seven species 5 were belonging with family cyprinidae, order cypriniformes while one species belong from order Anguilliformes family Anguillidae and one species belong with order Siluridae. (Khan, Zuberi, Fernandes, Ullah, & Sarwar, 2017) present a fish fauna survey on Barandu river dam they reported 7 species which were belong to 3 order, and 4 families cyprinidae is the richest family among the 7 species .The reason for high abundance of the Cyprinidae family was that environmental conditions were favourable for all Cyprinidae species in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa warm water Hatcheries. Carp species like *Cyprinus carpio* are relatively easy to breed in warm water hatcheries, which can result in higher reproduction rates. *Cyprinus carpio* are

known for its adaptability to various environmental conditions and water quality making suitable for aquaculture in different regions including Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Government support and consider preference to carp farming in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa region can lead to increased production. Thus the abundance of *cyprinidae* species throughout the study period was indicating that the habitat and environmental conditions of KPK warm water hatcheries were more suitable for growth and reproductive successes than the other species.

current research study was closely related to (Ferdous, Amin, Hasan, Alam, & Shahjahan, 2023) study of physiochemical parameters of water and soil on Sharki dam in Teri District Karak. The maximum temperature recorded of Sharki dam 35 °C, minimum temperature was 33 °C and the mean value was 34 °C. The temperature between 32°C to 35°C was great importance for fish growth and survival. The little deviation of Kohat hatchery 37 °C was due to surrounding weather and climate change, different study period and geographic area. (Britton, 2023) conducted a study on the seasonal variation of the physiochemical and biological Aspects of Indus River Pakistan. They recorded that the minimum temperature of 0°C in winter months while the maximum temperature of water was 36.67 °C in the Month of July. It was evident from the presents results that water temperature shows a seasonal variation within acceptable normal range. According to that the suitable water temperature of warm water carp fish culture was between 28 °C and 36 °C.

Conclusions

From the obtained study it was concluded that water quality shows suitability for varieties of fishes such as Cypriniformes family was the most abundant from the rest Anguilliformes and Siluriformes families which were least abundant in all warm water fish species in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Hatcheries. The findings of current breeding practices of Rohu (*Labeo rohita*) and Mori (*Cirrhinus mrigala*) showed maximum spawning response, maximum hatching and successful fertilization. It was due to practical

support and training made available by Government Hatcheries. All water quality parameters i.e. Temperature, Dissolve Oxygen, pH, Total Dissolve Solids, Turbidity and Ammonia concentration were favorable in normal range. A little fluctuation shows but it has no adverse effect on survival, reproduction, and growth of aquatic fish fauna. In Mardan and D.I Khan Hatcheries laboratory equipment's was present but have no proper laboratory. Kohat Hatchery have a great surface area and other were least surface areas.

Recommendations

Following recommendations may be made based on finding of current practices and fish fauna of Warm Water Fish hatcheries in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Public sector hatcheries although working efficiently but still needs a lot of improvement in terms of technical awareness and practical implementations. Government was spending a lot of budget but still Government Hatcheries face the problems of incomplete staff, electricity, unavailability of laboratories and least surface area of hatchery. The government was reported to overcome these basic problems and improves hatcheries production and boosted the financial system of the country. For maintenance and best production of hatchery, healthy brooders, fries and fingerlings must be reared with adequate food, optimum temperature and proper water supply. It was necessary to develop more attractiveness in fisheries professionals to culture more fish species in that hatcheries to produce more diverse groups of fish species and increase food resources.

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